

Roman Science Inspired By Emerging JWST Results

Conference Program 20-23 June 2023

TUESDAY

The morning is reserved for travel as an observance of the Juneteenth holiday. Sessions will begin at 1pm.

Session 1

Time	Title	Speaker
1 to 1:15pm	Welcome to STScI	Nancy Levenson
1:15 to 1:50pm	Roman Science and Mission Updates	Julie McEnery
1:50 to 2:10pm	Engaging with Roman	Karoline Gilbert
2:10 to 3pm	Juneteenth Celebration: the History of Harriet Tubman, the Underground Railroad, and Emancipation in Maryland	Linda Harris

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 3:00 to 3:30pm

Session 2: Surveys of the Very Nearby Universe

Time	Title	Speaker
3:30 to 4pm	Exoplanet Science with JWST & Roman: A Journey through Space and Time	Samuel Grunblatt
4 to 4:15pm	Exoplanet characterization synergies between JWST and Roman	Nestor Espinoza
4:15 to 4:30pm	Finding Planets with Roman and JWST	Julien Girard
4:30 to 4:45pm	Eta Tel B: 20 years of follow-up	Pedro Henrique Soares da Silva de Pinho Nogueira
4:45 to 5:15pm	Discovery and Characterization of Small Bodies in the Solar System	Rosemary Pike
5:15 to 5:30pm	Poster Lightning talks	Poster Presenters

Poster Session 1 from 5:30 to 6:30pm

Astronomy on Tap Event at Guilford Hall Brewery from 7 to about 10:30pm

Please join a special Astronomy on Tap event with the [Baltimore Astronomy on Tap group](#) at [Guilford Hall Brewery](#). Astronomy on Tap is usually very well attended (120 typical but 200+ in some cases) and has 3 Astro talks with breaks for trivia, games, and prizes!

WEDNESDAY

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 9:30 to 10am

Session 3: Surveys within the Milky Way and Nearby Galaxies

Time	Title	Speaker
10 to 10:15am	Revealing the Large-Scale Kinematic Structure of the Galactic Center with the Roman Space Telescope	Matthew Hosek
10:15 to 10:30	The origin of the very metal-rich stars near the sun	Ankita Mondal
10:30 to 10:45am	Brown and Red Dwarfs Identified in NIR Imaging	Benne Willem Holwerda
10:45 to 11:15	Near-field Cosmology with Roman and JWST	Nitya Kallivayalil
11:15 to 12pm	Interactive Discussion	SOC Moderator

Lunch provided in the Café from 12 to 1pm

Session 4: Galaxy Surveys at High Redshift

Time	Title	Speaker
1 to 1:30pm	Probing the Early Universe using the Most Distant Quasars	Jinyi Yang
1:30 to 1:45pm	A Comprehensive JWST Study on Galaxies at $z \sim 9-16$ and Its Implication for the Roman Surveys	Yuichi Harikane
1:45 to 2pm	Gravitationally lensed quasars in the reionization era: the prospective for the Roman Telescope	Minghao Yue
2 to 2:15pm	Predicting the Yields of $z > 6.5$ Quasar Surveys in the Era of Roman and Rubin	Wei Leong Tee
2:15 to 2:30pm	Probing the host galaxies of first quasars at $z \sim 7.5$ with JWST data	Weizhe Liu
2:30 to 3pm	Surveys of Galaxies at High Redshift with JWST and Roman	Micaela Bagley

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 3:00 to 3:30pm

Science Writers Workshop led by the STScI Office of Public Outreach from 3:30 to 5pm

Conference Reception with refreshments provided and a cash bar from 5 to 7pm

THURSDAY

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 9:30 to 10am

Session 5: Surveys of Nearby Galaxies

Time	Title	Speaker
10 to 10:30am	Stellar populations, and observation cosmology with Roman and JWST	Myung Gyoon Lee
10:30 to 10:45	Revealing the Merger Histories of Nearby Galaxies from their Stellar Halos with Roman	Adam Smercina
10:45 to 11am	Distances with Surface Brightness Fluctuations (SBF) and Globular Cluster Luminosity Functions (GCLF) with JWST and Roman	Nandini Hazra
11 to 11:15am	Unveiling the Low Surface Brightness Universe with Roman	Mireia Montes
11:15 to 11:30	Below the iceberg: Low surface brightness astronomy with HST, Euclid, and Roman	Alejandro S. Borlaff
11:30 to 11:45	A search for AGN in Green Peas in the local universe	Mainak Singha
11:45 to 12pm	Massively Multiplexed Spectroscopy with the Prime Focus Spectrograph in the Era of JWST and Roman	Jenny Greene

Lunch provided in the Café from 12 to 1pm

Session 6: Surveys of the flickering universe and galaxy formation

Time	Title	Speaker
1 to 1:30pm	Here, There, Everywhere: Strongly Lensed Supernovae, JWST, and Roman	Patrick Kelly
1:30 to 1:45pm	Guiding future deep-wide Roman surveys with galaxy formation physics we learn from JWST	Aaron Yung
1:45 to 2pm	Representing cosmic structures with graph neural networks	John Wu
2:15 to 2:30pm	Let's Go Extreme with Roman: Observing $Z \sim 0.5-2$ low and high EW ELGs	Ali Ahmad Khostovan
2:30 to 2:45pm	Anchoring Future Roman Deep Fields with COSMOS-Web: large scale structure to transients	Caitlin Casey
2:45 to 3pm	Poster Lightning Talks	Poster Presenters

Poster Session 2 from 3:30 to 4:30pm

STScI Public Lecture

The public lecture will focus on the legacy of Nancy Grace Roman and her role as namesake of the Roman Mission. The two speakers are Joan Yvonne Gordon, a family friend of Nancy Grace Roman, and Dr. Rachael Beaton, a member of the Roman team at STScI.

Conference Organized Dinner Event at 6pm

FRIDAY

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 9:30 to 10am

Session 7: Surveys of Galaxies before and around Cosmic Noon

Time	Title	Speaker
10 to 10:30am	New Insights on Luminous Infrared Galaxies from JWST	Vivian U
10:30 to 11am	Galaxies Evolution with Space-Based Slitless Spectroscopy: Past, Present, and Roman	Jasleen Matharu
11 to 11:15am	ESpRESSO: high-fidelity realistic grism simulations for Roman Space Telescope	Austen Gabrielpillai
11:15 to 11:30am	The Power of NIRCcam/Grism Wide Field Slitless Spectroscopy (WFSS) Observations: Early Results and Implications for Roman	Eiichi Egami
11:30 to 11:45	Planning for Roman: Case Study of Wide-field Slitless Grism Spectroscopy with JWST	Gaël Noirot

Lunch provided in the Café from 12 to 1pm

Session 8: Cosmology and Large Scale Surveys

Time	Title	Speaker
1 to 1:30pm	Weak lensing with JWST and Roman: Current Insights and Future Synergies	Ami Choi
1:30 to 1:45pm	Population III Protostar Variability in an Elliptical Orbit	Jongwon Park
1:45 to 2pm	Using Roman Space Telescope to find Dark Star candidates	Cosmin Ilie
2 to 2:15pm	Lyman-alpha at Cosmic Dawn with the LAGER survey and the Roman Space Telescope	Isak Wold
2:15 to 2:30pm	Prospects on Mapping Ionized Bubbles and Tracing the Global Evolution of the Ionized Structures during the Epoch of Reionization with Roman Space Telescope	Intae Jung
2:30 to 2:45pm	Roman Data Processing: Lessons Learned from JWST	Henry Ferguson

Coffee Break with refreshments provided from 3:00 to 3:30pm

Conference Summary from 3:30 to 4pm